

THE ALKALOID OF *RAUWOLFIA CANESCENS*, LINN. PART IV. ON THE
CONSTITUTION OF RAUWOLSCINE

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Rauwolscine, the alkaloid of *Rauwolfia canescens*, Linn., when distilled with zinc dust gives *iso*-quinoline, harman and skatole.

The skeletal structure (I) has previously been suggested for rauwolscine, the alkaloid of *Rauwolfia canescens*, Linn. (Mookerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 33) and has been based on a study of its reactions, properties and its degradation into harman, *iso*-phthalic acid, 3-ethyl-indole and indole-2-acid (Mookerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 485; 1943, 20, 11).

The rings A, B, C and E in (I) could be definitely established by the isolation of harman and *iso*phthalic acid but no definite evidence could be produced for the presence of ring D. The union of the *cycloparaffin* rings D, E through the tertiary nitrogen atom was assumed to explain the properties and reactions of the base and also in view of the similarity of the degradation products obtained from yohimbine and rauwolscine (Mookerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 33, 485; 1943, 20, 11). In search of some positive evidence of the presence of ring D, rauwolscine has been subjected to further degradations. The results are discussed in the present communication.

Rauwolscine on distillation with zinc dust gives *iso*quinoline, harman and skatole. Now, *iso*quinoline (II) can only originate through fission of the alkaloid at the dotted line.

The ring AB being an indole residue may be expected to produce quinolines but not *iso*quinolines. The formation of *iso*quinoline is regarded as a definite proof of the presence of ring D in rauwolscine.

EXPERIMENTAL

Zinc dust distillation of Rauwolscine.—Rauwolscine (8 g.) was mixed up with zinc dust (40 g.) and heated strongly in a combustion tube over free flame, the air having been previously replaced from the system by a current of hydrogen. The reaction mass was kept stirred by rotating the tube which was heated up to redness within 10 minutes.

The heating was continued for 1 hour. The products of distillation were passed through a 5% solution of hydrochloric acid. When the tube cooled down, the residue in the tube was thrice digested with ether (50 c.c. each time). The red ethereal digest was mixed up with the hydrochloric acid solution containing other products of distillation mentioned above and shaken energetically in a separating funnel. In this way two fractions were obtained: An aqueous acid solution (a) and an ethereal fraction (b).

The wine coloured acid solution (a) was basified with aqueous sodium hydroxide when a viscid mass separated. It was taken up in ether and the ether layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained after removal of ether was subjected to high vacuum distillation when it yielded two fractions, distilling at 65-70°/0.3 mm. and at 160-80°/0.1 mm. respectively.

Isolation of isoquinoline.—The fraction boiling at 65-70° was a pale yellow liquid (0.35 g.) having a quinoline like odour. It was purified by redistillation in *vacuo* at 65-70°/0.3 mm. The liquid when freshly distilled was colourless but gradually turned brown on exposure to air. With an ethereal solution of picric acid, the liquid produced a yellow precipitate which crystallised from alcohol in shining yellow needles, m.p. 215-17°, (decomp.). [Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* at 100° for 4 hours over P₂O₅: N, 15.72. C₉H₇N.C₆H₂(NO₂)₃OH requires N, 15.64 per cent]. It showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with a specimen of the picrate of synthetic isoquinoline.

Chloroplatinate of isoquinoline.—An aqueous solution of platinum chloride (5%) was slowly added to an aqueous solution of the above isoquinoline (0.25 c.c.) dissolved in hydrochloric acid. The orange precipitate was collected and washed with cold water containing a little hydrochloric acid. The precipitate crystallised from water in shining orange needles, m.p. 262-64° (decomp.). [Found at 100°: Pt, 29.35. (C₉H₇N)₂. H₂PtCl₆ requires Pt, 29.18 per cent]. It showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with a specimen of the chloroplatinate of synthetic isoquinoline.

Isolation of Harman.—The pale yellow viscid mass which distilled at 160-80°/0.1 mm. was extracted with hydrochloric acid (1%). The major portion of the distillate dissolved, leaving only a little gummy mass. The solution was filtered and basified with an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide and the base liberated was drawn into ether. The ethereal solution was again extracted with hydrochloric acid, the base was liberated from the acid solution and this process of purifying the base was repeated thrice. The purified base was obtained as a semisolid mass and was distilled in *vacuo* when a pale yellow solid (0.12 g.) sublimed at 160-80°/0.1 mm. The sublimate crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 230°. (Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 4 hours at 110°: C, 79.2; H, 5.43; N, 15.40. C₁₂H₁₀N₂ requires C, 79.12; H, 5.49; N, 15.38 per cent). The melting point did not change when the crystals were mixed with a synthetic specimen of harman.

Isolation of Skatole from the ethereal fraction (b).—The ethereal solution (b) was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained after evaporation of ether yielded on steam distillation, a pale yellow oil with a faecal smell like that of skatole. The oil distilled at 100-110°/0.1 mm. and formed a pale yellow solid,

m.p. 90° on cooling (0.15 g.). On repeated crystallisations from benzene it melted at 93° . The oil turned gradually red when exposed to air. It imparted a red colour to a pine chip moistened with concentrated hydrochloric acid. Mixed with skatole there was no depression in m.p. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 4 hours at 60° : C, 82.63; H, 7.12; N, 10.93. C_9H_9N requires C, 82.43; H, 6.87; N, 10.09 per cent). With picric acid it produced a scarlet-red picrate which crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. $169-71^{\circ}$ (decomp.). [Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 4 hours at 100° : N, 15.12. $C_9H_9N.C_6H_2OH(NO_2)_3$ requires N, 15.55 per cent). The picrate showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with skatole picrate which melted alone at 172° .

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